

Beyond the Chalkboard

Developed by: Technische Hochschule Köln - University of Applied Sciences & Spoonful Games

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Keywords

Accessibility, Anxiety, Depression, Educational Ethics, Empathy, Inclusion, Mental Health, Psychology, Trauma

Introduction

Beyond the Chalkboard is a browser-based serious game released by TH Köln, University of Applied Sciences, in September 2025 (ZLE, n.d.). It aims to make higher education accessible by raising awareness of the structural and emotional challenges faced by students with mental health issues (Alfeld et al., 2025a). The game is designed primarily for university staff – especially lecturers, professors, and others involved in teaching students. The point-and-click game allows players to experience three days in the life of Sam, a student struggling with a mental illness. You make decisions such as whether to go to university or stay at home, study for an exam or meet up with friends, take a walk or take a shower – shaping Sam’s everyday life. However, players’ choices and experiences are limited by systemic conditions, the behaviour of teachers and fellow students, as well as Sam’s fears and depressive feelings.

Facts

Release date:	09/2025
Developer:	Technische Hochschule Köln-University of Applied Sciences & Spoonful Games
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	30–45 minutes
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Access to a computer (Using a mouse/touchpad and ideally sound/headphones). Playing on a tablet is also possible, but not ideal.
Material:	All important instructions can be found on the website. There is a didactic guide you can use to implement the game in workshops.
Price:	Available free of charge

Resonance & Criticism

As the game was only released in September 2025, player feedback is still limited. However, students with mental illnesses were involved in the development process as experts by experience. They tested the game at three different stages, provided feedback, and shared their personal experiences to help shape the game content. It was made clear that a game cannot fully capture the life of a student with mental illness, but the experts appreciated the insights it offered.

Game Principle & Process

Figure 1. Screenshot from *Beyond the Chalkboard* (2025). © Technische Hochschule Köln – University of Applied Sciences & Spoonful Games.

The setting of *Beyond the Chalkboard* is Sam's apartment (see Figure 1) and places on the university campus. Players see Sam in a seminar room, in a lecture hall, and socializing with other students at the benches. By left-clicking, players can move Sam, interact with objects and people, and respond in text-based dialogues. A central gameplay mechanic is the mind space, where Sam's thoughts and feelings are visually represented. These thoughts move around the mind space and change size depending on their urgency. Sam's current emotional state affects the accessibility of the mind space, which appears as a fog that shrinks the active area. Thoughts and feelings hidden in the fog cannot be reached, meaning the player cannot select corresponding actions. Positive experiences help to reduce the fog. Players can also move thoughts and feelings around using a drag-and-drop function. An introductory tutorial provides further details about this mechanic. The mind space feature illustrates how events,

interactions, and player choices affect Sam's state of mind. Depending on the decisions made, the game features multiple possible endings.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The aim of Beyond the Chalkboard is to raise awareness among lecturers and other university staff about the challenges faced by students with mental health issues, thereby helping make their teaching more accessible (Alfeld et al., 2025a). Playing the game allows participants to immerse themselves in the world of such a student and gain deeper insight from the student's perspective. The game can be played independently but is ideally accompanied by a workshop (Alfeld et al., 2025b). In the suggested workshop, participants are encouraged to reflect on possible actions to improve accessibility. After playing, ideally, they understand to what extent barriers are systemic rather than individual. From this perspective, they explore ways to design inclusive teaching practices that contribute to a more accessible higher education environment for students with mental illnesses. Accompanying the game website is a facilitator's guide offering several adaptable elements that can be customized to suit different workshop needs (Alfeld et al., 2025b):

- Introduction and Goals
- Playing Beyond the Chalkboard
- Personal Reflection on the Gaming Experience
- Exchange and Discussion: Mental Illness in Teaching
- Studying with a Mental Illness
- Developing Action Strategies
- Consolidation and Conclusion

Effectiveness

No empirical studies on the game's effectiveness have been conducted yet.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Beyond the Chalkboard is designed to help players empathize with a student experiencing depression and anxiety. This may be triggering for some players. Players are advised to be mindful of their needs while playing and seek support if necessary. If playing in a group, players

should be mindful of the topic's sensitivity. The game's website provides links to German-language support resources. This information should be shared when using the game in an educational or didactic setting.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl

Sources

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